

USING THE CASE METHOD IN THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING HUMAN CAPITAL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317683>

During the years of self-government in Uzbekistan, the case-study prodecery is gradually becoming favored through the educational system. The wide use of this method in exercise, especially in resolving setbacks and making decisions in handling, will bear its fruit. Also, this method has positive significance in the development of human capital. The case-study tactic allows to study and analyze any situation. It embraces elements that reflect the general nature of the process in solving a problem situation.

It is said that the "Case-study" method in English means "case" – suitcase, method, "study" – problem situation, situation, including situation, case analysis or problem situation analysis. Currently, it is used as a technology that serves to form the skills of finding the most optimal options by analyzing a specific, real problem situation. The teaching technique used in the description of real situations implies the design of the case technology.

The case-study technology was first used in the educational process in 1870 at Harvard University Law School in the USA as an experiment to study problematic cases. After the positive effect of this technology was clearly demonstrated, it was used in the business school of the university in 1920. The first collection of cases was published in 1925 in the Harvard Business Reports. Currently, this technology is widely used in foreign countries in the fields of economy and business. Efforts to implement this technology in the educational process in Uzbekistan began in the early years of independence.

There are also ready-made versions of cases used in the management process in the West. They can even be bought. However, the most effective way is to achieve independent creation of cases for each area. According to data, 700 cases are developed annually at Harvard University. They include projects priced from \$10 to \$1,000. The London Business School and other business schools are engaged in creating cases, bringing together about 340 participants. This practice definitely pays off. Instead of wrong, superficial or periodic solutions to various problems, it allows to have grounded, clear, goal-oriented, useful solutions.

This technology develops interest in mastering the subject, practical skills, skills of creative approach to situation analysis and making the right decision. Creates a variety of problem situations and the possibility of solving them.

The main tasks of this technology are shown below:

- development of analytical skills and critical thinking;
- ensuring unity of theory and practice;
- to demonstrate different views and approaches to the problem;
- making decisions and providing comments on their consequences;
- formation of skills to evaluate alternative options in the presence of uncertainties.

Of course, it is important to check and evaluate the cases in order to achieve a positive result in advance. The created case must undergo expert review and evaluation. The review of the case project by the employee of the enterprise and the compliance of the information stated in it with the real situation, as well as the interpretation of the given facts and the like can be used as verification methods.

With the help of case study, it is possible to acquire the following knowledge, skills and abilities:

- analytical skills - to be able to separate information from information, categorize them, divide them into necessary and secondary levels according to their importance, analyze, present, for this a person must be able to think clearly and logically;

- practical skills - being able to analyze the real situation based on the complexity of the problem, to be able to apply the most important theories, methods and principles;

- creative skills - it is not important to solve the situation and problem based on logic, but to find several solutions to the problem based on a creative approach and analyze them;

- communication skills - it is necessary to be able to master the skills of arguing, defending one's point of view, convincing others of one's decision, preparing a very short and convincing report;

- social skills - one must be able to analyze the behavior of others during the discussion of the decision, to be able to listen to others, to support the opinions of others in the debate, to be able to express an opposite opinion to the proposed opinion, and to be able to control oneself;

- self-analysis - it is important to be able to control oneself during the debate process, to be an example to others;

- it is necessary to be able to achieve thorough justification of each case assignment.

In order for the case assignments to have a practical-didactic character, it is necessary to pay attention to the following when developing them:

- clearly expressing the purpose, that is, the purpose should not be understood in two or more ways;

- that the questions or tasks are somewhat complicated;

- be able to cover several aspects of social, economic, cultural life;

- does not quickly lose its practical significance;

- able to show national characteristics;

- to be relevant;

- development of analytical thinking;

- create an opportunity to organize a debate;

- to be able to provide the possibility of advancing several solutions (decisions).

It is known that human life is formed in the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities that can be improved with the help of investments. T. Shults, one of the founders of the theory of human capital, justifies the following types of capital depending on the form of investments:

- development of the educational process;

- development based on work, labor skills;

- health care, health promotion;

- growing knowledge and skills in the fields of economy.¹
- development of the educational process;
- development based on work, labor skills;
- health care, health promotion;
- growing knowledge and skills in the fields of economy.

And G. Becker in his scientific views explained the unity of his knowledge, skills a Thus, both scientists agree that human capital can be sold in the labor market. The accumulation of such capital requires a lot of time, a large amount of expenses, complex investments:

- long-term benefit;
- feature related to fixed costs;
- physical aging is associated with the loss of useful properties and motivations through human capital.²

In the theory of human capital, G. Becker introduced the concept of internal rate of return, which has individual and social characteristics. First, it describes the introduction of investments from the point of view of specific investors, and secondly, it evaluates their effectiveness from the point of view of society as a whole. Therefore, the rate of return, in turn, appears as a regulator of the distribution of investments between different types and levels of education, and between the education system in its various sectors of the economy as a whole.

In the works of G. Becker, as well as in the works of T. Shults, investments in human capital significantly increase compared to investments in physical capital. American economist L. Turov examines human capital from the point of view of productivity in his research. It defines human capital as the ability of people to produce goods and services. It affects not only individual production investment, but also the effectiveness of other investments.³ P. Romer is also a supporter of this approach and interprets human capital as the main source of increasing economic efficiency. He emphasized that human capital is the source of new knowledge.⁴

In the development of human capital, deductive thinking is important. It can be used for transitioning from a general concept to a concrete idea, for forming independent, critical, analytical thinking in young people, for acquiring a necessary logical feature, and also for demonstrating various forms of social relations.

It is known that axioms are theoretical opinions that are accepted as true without proof, and by means of which other opinions and opinions are justified. Deductive reasoning is in the form of syllogism. The axiom of syllogism expresses the logical validity of the conclusion. The axiom of the syllogism can be defined according to the size or content of the terms, i.e. attributive. The axiom of the syllogism can be expressed as follows: "If one thing is inside the second thing, and the second thing is inside the third thing, then the first thing is also inside the third thing" or "If one thing is inside the second thing, and the second thing is

¹ Schultz, T. W. Investment in Human Capital / T.W. Schultz // The American Economic Review. 1961. Vol. 51. Pr. 1–17.

² Becker G. Human capital (book chapters). Impact of human capital investment on income. USA: Economy, Politics, Ideology, 1993. - No. 11.

³ Thurow L. Investment in Human Capital. Belmont, 1970. -104 p.

⁴ Romer P. Endogenous Technological Change // Journal of Political Economy.- 1990, Vol. 98(5). -P. 71–102.

outside of the third thing" if there is, then the first item will also be located outside the third item". This rule can be clearly expressed using the forms in the melody.⁵

Analogy (Greek - conformity, similarity) is a type of indirect inference. In deductive reasoning, the idea moves from the general to the specific, in induction from the specific to the general, in analogy, a conclusion is made based on the similar signs of objects and events.

In the development of human capital, a conclusion is made based on similar properties of objects in analogy. Along with objective diversity in nature and society, there is also objective similarity. They are expressed in the human mind. If the laws and rules related to different spheres of objective reality are similar in structure, then the different things and events in the reality they reflect are also similar in a certain sense. Drawing a conclusion on analogy is based on similarities in properties, relationships, and contents of various systems of objective reality. For example, there is a similarity in the essence of planets, states, social systems. A conclusion is made by analogy based on the similarity of important and unimportant properties in cognition.

When I. Kepler discovered the law of planetary motion, he compared the mutual attraction of celestial bodies to the love between people, on this basis he introduced the concept of gravity to astronomy. The formula for the analogy of relations is as follows:

In the analogy of relations, a conclusion is drawn not about the similarity of two objects, but about the relationship between two other objects based on the work that built the relationship between two objects.

The experiences of economically developed countries such as Great Britain, the USA, the European Union, Canada, Japan, China, Russia and Turkey, as well as the practice of a number of international organizations, including the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the UN New Millennium Development Program (UN New Millennium Goal), UN Development Program "Sustainable Development Goal" (UNDP Sustainable Development Goal), Human Development Indices and Indicators (Human Development Indices and Indicators), ILO, International Labor Conference, ILO, International Ergonomics Association, UN Industrial Development Organization, International Organization for Standardization, Global Professional Health and Safety Coalition (The Global Coalition for Safety and Health at Work), International Commission on Occupational Health (International Commission on Occupational Health), Sanitation and Hygiene Fund within the UN, International Social Security Association (ISSA), Human Development Indicators and Criteria (Human Development Indices and Indicators), World Social Protection Report, Global Trends: Emerging Construction Labor Markets, Global forecasts of the construction industry for 2030 (A global forecast for the construction industry to 2030), Human Resources Annual Report (Human Resources Annual Report), Human Resources Report (Human Resources Report), Human Development Index (Human Development Index), Inclusive Development Index (The Inclusive Development Index).

According to our compatriot, encyclopedist Abu Raykhan Beruniy, "the most important idea is that all valuable things are created by human labor, and the value of a person is

⁵ Becker G.S. Human Behavior: An Economic Approach: Selected Works in Economic Theory. - M.: GU VSHE, 2003. - 672.

determined not by who his ancestors were, but by his labor, mental and physical skills”⁶ puts forward the idea that.

A problem situation in solving a case is the interaction between the subject of knowledge and the object of scientific research, creation of inventions, and thought directed at obtaining new knowledge. There are simple signs of a problem situation, which consists of asking oneself questions about unclear problems, looking for ways and means to solve it.

A problematic situation arises when contradictions are identified. In this case, the answer to the question that resolves this contradiction is unknown. It is a problem. The components of the problematic situation are:

- subject of knowledge;
- teaching subject;
- the subject of knowledge;
- dialogue between the problem-setter and listeners;
- listener's need to know;
- mental interaction of the listener with the content of knowledge.

It is important to effectively apply the capabilities of the case method in the development of human capital in management. By investing in human development, society can achieve not only increased labor productivity, but also more equitable distribution of goods, social products and services. Thus, the task of developing human capital in order to achieve the goals of economic modernization is a priority of the state's social policy. The new development strategy of Uzbekistan is also important for its alignment with these goals and objectives.

Every investment in civil society support ensures that people are creative and law-abiding. An atmosphere of optimism is created in the society, a constructive and rational outlook is formed. Non-governmental institutions that improve the quality of life will appear. People learn to live a healthy lifestyle. All this creates confidence in the future in our people and improves the quality of life.

⁶ Balabanov I. T. Innovative management. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2000.

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